

EXAMINING THE ROLE OF COLLEGE DEANS' SUPERVISORY PRACTICES IN EFFECTIVE POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Kenneth Albano Abalos, MAEd

Department of Arts and Sciences, Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14166657>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the supervisory practices of college deans at Isabela State University, Cabagan Campus, and their relationship to effective policy implementation, as perceived by deans and faculty. Employing a descriptive correlational-comparative design, it focused on supervisory practices in areas such as classroom supervision, in-service education, and community service, while also assessing policy implementation regarding promotion, rewards systems, and professional development. Data from five deans and 91 teachers were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, t-tests, and Pearson's correlation. Results indicate that while deans generally had high educational qualifications and supervisory experience, there was a notable difference in how deans and teachers perceived supervisory effectiveness, particularly in teacher evaluation. Findings suggest that fostering transparent evaluation practices and collaborative relationships between deans and faculty can improve policy implementation, with recommendations to enhance mentorship, inter-departmental collaboration, and professional development initiatives.

Keywords: *Supervisory practices, Policy implementation, College deans, Descriptive correlational-comparative design, Professional development, Teacher evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Management is essential at all levels of an organization, encompassing planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling efforts to achieve specific goals (Lloyd & Aho, 2020). Goal-oriented approaches in organizations, including schools, can significantly

enhance productivity and knowledge management. Employees with a learning goal orientation (LGO) are more likely to engage in knowledge sharing, while those with a performance-prove goal orientation (PPGO) are less inclined to do so (Kim & Kim, 2023). Research indicates that leadership styles significantly impact organizational performance and team collaboration across diverse environments. Transformational and collaborative leadership approaches have been shown to influence organizational performance and job satisfaction positively. Transformational leadership fosters a positive organizational climate, enhances job satisfaction, and improves team performance (Gaviria-Rivera & López-Zapata, 2019). Supervision plays a crucial role in guiding human resources and improving organizational performance, with recent studies highlighting its positive effects on employee performance and job satisfaction (Netra et al., 2024).

Effective administration is crucial for organizational efficiency and progress in educational institutions. Administrators coordinate resources, plan strategies, and ensure goal attainment (Aniagboso, 2020; Aloyzius & Kindiki, 2020). School managers are responsible for actions that contribute to group objectives, and their management style can indicate the likelihood of team success or failure (Akın & Erdem, 2022). Working with people in educational organizations and effective supervision requires a deep understanding of human behavior (Sergiovanni, 2009). As one management expert observed, “If you dig very deeply into any problems, you will get people” (Bolman & Deal, 2017). This perspective emphasizes the importance of school administrators connecting with their subordinates to facilitate effective collaboration.

Personnel management is essential for the success of educational institutions, involving careful planning, training, and regular evaluation of educators and staff (Cahyati et al., 2024). School leaders play a vital role in organizing and directing personnel to improve school quality (Al Farizi & Patimah, 2023). When principals manage teachers diplomatically, recognize their contributions, and employ effective techniques for organizing, directing, coordinating, and controlling, a positive personnel system is fostered (Francis & Oluwatoyin, 2019). A pleasant organizational atmosphere motivates teachers and staff to perform at their best (Shen, 2019).

School administrators must balance authority and influence to lead educational institutions effectively. Research suggests that moderate influence tactics create an efficient work environment and increase teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviors, while harsher tactics can lead to negative attitudes and low motivation (Korkmaz & Koşar, 2023). Authority in educational settings should be viewed as a dynamic, socially constructed relationship rather than a top-down command structure (Harjunen, 2009; Pace & Hemmings, 2006). As Cotton (2003) noted, a middle school manager can either create a dull environment or make even small details significant and enjoyable.

The success of administrators largely depends on their teachers’ performance (Acera et al., 2023). Regardless of how effectively a principal executes school policies and programs, indifferent or uncommitted teachers can render those efforts ineffective (Fullan, 2001). Effective school management requires principals to recognize that supervision is not merely inspection or coercion; rather, it is a service aimed at

cooperatively improving all factors affecting student development (Wang & Holcombe, 2010). Consequently, every school needs some form of supervisory program.

Many teachers possess untapped potential that can significantly enhance their effectiveness (Woods & Wright, 2015). However, factors such as poor human relations, inadequate personnel administration, and an inability to evaluate their work may prevent teachers from fully utilizing their skills and talents (Glickman et al., 2018). The supervisory function in schools should spark self-motivation among teachers, focusing on the learner as the center of the educational process (Oyewole & Alonge, 2013).

At Isabela State University, deans are considered supervisors who directly oversee teachers' daily activities. Supervision is a crucial aspect of educational management, particularly for college deans and department chairs who hold diverse positions within the institutional hierarchy. These administrators face challenges in managing relationships with faculty, students, and superiors, while overseeing both in-person and online learning environments (Schwanenberger et al., 2021). They bear significant responsibilities and interact with top management, such as the President and Vice President (Goldring & Sims, 2005). Deans monitor activities, solicit information, and disseminate it to subordinates (Davis, 2015).

Academic leadership in higher education is a complex role that requires balancing strategic vision with daily operational tasks. Deans face pressures related to accountability measures, student enrollment, and government mandates (Bosetti & Heffernan, 2021). Interpersonal and negotiating skills are essential for deans to work effectively with various stakeholders for different purposes (Wepner et al., 2014). The visibility of deans to higher authorities is crucial for effective governance and leadership, as organizational stressors from higher authorities can impact their performance and the overall educational environment (Chan et al., 2018).

The role of educational administrators, especially deans, has become increasingly complex in recent years. These leaders must manage various stakeholders, including faculty, students, and external partners while balancing administrative and academic responsibilities (Anitsal et al., 2020). The Isabela State University (ISU) system comprises six campuses, each headed by a campus director, while each college is overseen by a college dean. With most colleges and programs located on the Cabagan Campus, this study focuses on the deans of the various programs there, as they play a pivotal role in supervision, which is the central focus of this study.

Research Questions

This study assessed the supervisory practices of Isabela State University College Deans as perceived by themselves and the faculty members. It looked into how management policies are implemented.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the college deans in terms of:
 - A. Socio-Demographic Characteristics

- a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Religion
 - d. Ethnicity
 - e. Length of service
 - f. Family structure
- B. Professional Characteristics
- a. highest educational attainment
 - b. designations held
 - c. seminars and trainings
2. How do the college deans and teachers assess the formers' supervisory practices relative to:
- a. classroom supervision
 - b. in-service education
 - c. teacher evaluation
 - d. community service
 - e. physical plant evaluation
3. How different are the assessments of the two groups of respondents on the supervisory practices of the Deans when grouped by the college?
4. What is the perception of the college deans and the teachers on the implementation of management policies along the following:
- a. promotion
 - b. rewards system
 - c. professional development

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a descriptive correlational-comparative method. A descriptive presentation was made on the profile of the deans, while the correlational design was used to relate supervisory practices with the profile variables and management practices. The comparative design was utilized to compare the responses of the respondents.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Isabela State University (ISU), specifically in the five colleges of Cabagan Campus, Cabagan, Isabela. These colleges include the College of Development and College of Arts and Sciences (CDCAS), College of Forestry, Teachers' College, Provincial Technical Institute of Agriculture (PTIA), and the Graduate School.

Respondents and Sampling Method

The respondents of the study included all five deans and 91 teachers from the different colleges at Isabela State University, Cabagan, Isabela. Complete enumeration sampling was conducted for both groups of respondents.

Research Instruments

The questionnaire was the primary instrument used for gathering the necessary information in the study. It was divided into three parts. Part I elicited the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, religion, ethnicity, length of service, and family structure. It also included the professional characteristics of the deans regarding their highest educational attainment, designations held, and seminars and trainings attended. Part II focused on supervisory practices related to classroom supervision, in-service education, and teacher evaluation. Part III assessed policy implementation concerning promotion, professional development, and the rewards system. The supervisory practices were based on the study of Abaita (1994) but were modified according to the functions of the deans. Management policies were also based on the study of Urdas (1997), incorporating the suggestions of the panel members.

Collection of Data

The researcher requested permission to conduct and administer the questionnaires to the Campus Director of ISU, Cabagan Campus, and the College Deans of the different colleges through a letter of request. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered and retrieved the questionnaires, achieving a 100% retrieval rate.

Analysis of Data

Data on the profile variables, such as age, sex, religion, ethnicity, length of service, family structure, educational attainment, designations held, and seminars/trainings attended, were tabulated and analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. A t-test was used to test the significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents regarding the supervisory practices of the deans and the differences in responses when grouped by the college. Pearson's Moment of Correlation was utilized to compute the relationships between the variables studied.

The following 5-point Likert scale was used.

4.20-5.00	Always	Strongly Agree	Excellent
3.40-4.19	Often	Agree	Very Satisfactory
2.60-3.39	Occasionally	Uncertain	Satisfactory
1.80-2.59	Seldom	Disagree	Fair
1.00-1.79	Never	Strongly Disagree	Poor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

The socio-demographic characteristics of the deans are presented in Table 1. It shows that their ages range from 44 to 52, with a mean age of 46.6, suggesting that the deans are generally middle-aged. Regarding sex, only one (1) dean is male, while the rest are female. This may imply that females are more inclined to take on supervisory roles. Regarding religious affiliation, three (3) deans are Catholic, one (1) is Baptist, and one (1) identifies as Christian. In terms of ethnicity, all deans are Ibanag, which is expected as they all come from Cabagan, an Ibanag town in Isabela. Additionally, it was found that all deans are married, with children still dependent on them.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the college deans

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
44	2	40
45	1	20
49	1	20
52	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
Sex		
Male	1	20
Female	4	80
TOTAL	5	100
Religion		
Roman Catholic	3	60
Baptist	1	20
Christian	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
Ethnicity		
Ibanag	5	100
TOTAL	5	100
Length of Service		
25	1	20
27	2	40
29	1	20
32	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
Mean = 28 years		
Family Structure		
Married and with Dependent Children	5	100

TOTAL	5	100
-------	---	-----

Table 2 presents the professional characteristics of the college deans. It shows that all the deans hold doctorate degrees, which is expected given that, according to policies and standards, college deans must be Ph.D. or Ed.D. graduates. The same table also outlines the positions or designations held by the deans before their appointment. Two (2) deans were formerly department chairs, one (1) served as a Guidance Coordinator, one (1) was a supervisor of student teaching, and one (1) worked as a staff member of the development board. This indicates that they had supervisory experience prior to becoming deans.

Regarding local and regional training, four (4) deans had ten (10) training sessions, while only one (1) had fifteen (15). It is also worth noting that all of them have attended international seminars, with three (3) deans having attended four (4) seminars, and two (2) attending two (2) and three (3) international seminars, respectively.

Table 2. Professional Characteristics of the College Deans

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Ph.D.	5	5
TOTAL	5	100
Designation/Position Held		
Department Chair	2	40
Guidance Coordinator	1	20
Supervisor – Teacher Training	1	20
Member, Staff Development Board	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
No. of Local Seminars Attended		
10	4	80
15	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
No. of Regional Seminars Attended		
8	1	20
10	2	40
13	1	20
15	1	20
TOTAL	5	100
No. of International Seminars Attended		
2	1	20
3	1	20
4	3	60
TOTAL	5	100

Teachers' assessments and self-assessments of the supervisory practices of deans in relation to classroom supervision are presented in Table 3. The table indicates that all items were rated as "often," including "allows teachers and students to express their instructional needs" and "monitors the implementation of the innovative teaching-learning process." However, the deans assessed these practices as being done "occasionally." The overall weighted mean of teachers' assessments is 4.4, indicating "always," while the self-assessment had a weighted mean of 4.09, indicating "often." This suggests that teachers feel positively about their deans' classroom supervision, viewing it as a significant factor in the improvement of instruction.

On the other hand, the deans acknowledged that they often engage in these practices but noted that recommending appropriate tools, equipment, materials, and other instructional resources was only done occasionally. This limitation is attributed to budgetary constraints faced by the colleges.

College Deans and Teachers' Assessments on the Deans' Supervisory Practices

Table 3. Teachers' assessment and self-assessment on supervisory practices of the deans relative to classroom supervision.

Classroom Supervision Assessment	Teacher's Scale	Description	Dean's Scale	Description
1. Conduct class visitation and make observations	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
2. Encourage the punctuality of teachers in classrooms and all activities.	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
3. Check teachers:				
a. Lesson plan	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
b. Syllabi	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
c. Instructional Materials	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
4. Assist teachers or problems identified and help for diagnosis and treatment.	4.2	Always	3.8	Often
5. Recommend appropriate tools, equipment materials, and reference materials for instruction.	4.2	Always	3.2	Often
4. Elicit from teachers the kinds of help in the problems.	4.5	Always	3.4	Often
5. Allow teachers and students to express their instructional	4.1	Often	4.0	Often

needs.				
6. Monitor the implementation of Innovative teaching Strategies that require teaching learning process	4.1	Often	4.0	Often
7. Supervise remedial teaching.	4.5	Always	3.6	Often
8. Direct safety measures about shop Instruction.	4.4	Always	3.8	Often
9. Encourage teachers to utilize Community resources for instruction.	4.5	Always	3.8	Often
TOTAL	4.4	Always	4.09	Often

Table 4 presents teachers' assessments and self-assessments of the deans' supervisory practices regarding in-service education. All items were assessed by teachers as "always," with a weighted mean of 4.5. In contrast, the deans assessed their supervisory practices related to in-service education as "often," with an overall weighted mean of 3.6.

When comparing the assessments of deans with those of teachers, the item "sends teachers to training, seminars, conferences, and workshops when there is a need and opportunity" received an occasional rating from the deans, reflected in a score of 3.2. The same rating was also given by the deans themselves for the item "encourage inter-class visitations among teachers." This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that not all teachers have the same access to training and seminars, as well as opportunities for inter-class visitations, since they must also stay updated on new trends and innovations.

Table 4. Teachers' assessment of supervisory practices of the deans relative to in-service education

Classroom Supervision Assessment	Teacher's Scale	Description	Dean's Scale	Description
1. Conduct individual and group conferences with teachers.	4.4	Always	4.0	Often
2. Organize training programs for teachers.	4.7	Always	4.0	Often
3. Encourage teachers to pursue their higher degree.	4.4	Always	4.0	Often
4. Send teachers to trainings, seminars, and workshops if there is a need or opportunity.	4.6	Always	3.6	Often

5. Discuss innovation in education during meetings.	4.6	Always	3.6	Often
6. Invite master teachers or experts to demonstrate effective teaching procedures.	4.3	Always	4.0	Often
7. Guide teachers for instructional improvements.	4.4	Always	3.4	Often
8. Encourage inter-classroom visitations among teachers	4.5	Always	3.2	Often
9. Encourage team teaching to improve instructional skills.	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
10. Boost participation in educational tours.	4.5	Always	3.6	Often
TOTAL	4.5	Always	4.5	Often

Table 5 reveals the teachers' assessments and self-assessments of the supervisory practices of the deans concerning teacher evaluation. It was found that all items related to teacher evaluation were assessed by the teachers as "always," with an overall weighted mean of 4.5. In contrast, the deans evaluated their supervisory practices related to teacher evaluation as "often," with a weighted mean of 4.0. This indicates that the two groups of respondents do not share the same perspective. Teachers rated their deans higher than the deans rated themselves, suggesting that teachers believe these practices are consistently implemented by their supervisors, even though they feel that evaluations should not occur all the time.

Table 5. Teachers' assessment and self-assessment on supervisory practices of the deans relative to teacher evaluation

Teacher Evaluation	Teacher's Assessment Scale	Description	Dean's Assessment Scale	Description
1. Check test questions of teachers	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
2. Require teachers to make a table of specifications.	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
3. Require teachers to disseminate test results.	4.7	Always	4.0	Often
4. Monitor student requirements and see to it that these are returned.	4.3	Always	4.0	Often
TOTAL	4.5	Always	4.0	Often

The teachers' assessments and self-assessments of the supervisory practices of the deans in relation to community service are shown in Table 6. Teachers evaluated the deans' community service as "always," with a weighted mean of 4.38, while the deans assessed their own community service as "often," with a weighted mean of 3.48. All items

were rated as “always” by teachers, except for the item regarding the collegial relationships of the deans with community organizations, which was rated as “often,” with a weighted mean of 4.1. The self-assessment of the deans regarding their initiation of community organizations was only 3.2, indicating that this is done only occasionally. This implies that the deans have already established some level of partnership with the community.

Table 6. Teachers’ assessment and self-assessment on supervisory practices of the deans relative to community service

Community Service	Teacher’s Assessment Scale	Description	Dean’s Assessment Scale	Description
1. Sees to it that the school gives direction to the needs of the community.	4.5	Always	2.4	Often
2. Initiate community organizations	4.3	Always	3.2	Often
3. Manifest collegial relationships with community organizations.	4.1	Always	3.6	Often
4. Work collaboratively with PTCA, GOs, and NGOs.	4.6	Always	3.6	Often
5. Provide technical support and assistance whenever there is a need or a request.	4.4	Always	3.6	Often
TOTAL	4.38	Always	3.48	Often

The teachers’ assessments and self-assessments of the supervisory practices of the deans concerning physical plant supervision are shown in Table 7. It can be gleaned that the teachers have relatively higher assessments of their deans’ performance in this aspect, with mean values equivalent to “Always.” This is further indicated by the overall mean of 4.33.

The deans exhibit modest self-assessment, yielding means that are described as “often” in performing physical plant supervision. This could be attributed to the fact that such a function is strongly supported and also carried out by university officials.

Table 7. Teachers’ assessment and self-assessment on supervisory practices of the deans relative to physical plant supervision

Physical Plant Supervision	Teacher’s Assessment Scale	Description	Dean’s Assessment Scale	Description
1. Checks periodically the buildings and other facilities.	4.6	Always	3.6	Often
2. Sees to it that the building and physical facilities are utilized properly.	4.0	Always	3.0	Often
3. Checks classrooms if they are conducive to learning.	4.6	Always	4.0	Often
4. Sees to it that teaching classrooms are safe and secured.	4.6	Always	3.6	Often
5. Ensures that there are safe, sufficient drinking water.	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
6. Shows responsibility in the care and maintenance of school site/buildings with teachers and students.	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
TOTAL	4.33	Always	3.83	Often

The summary table of the assessment of the two groups of respondents is shown in Table 8. It is clear that the teachers’ ratings are relatively higher, described as “always.” The supervisory practices regarding classroom supervision, in-service education, teacher evaluation, community service, and physical plant supervision are “always” performed by the deans.

On the other hand, the deans rated themselves as “often” in terms of their supervisory practices.

Table 8. Summary table of teachers’ assessment and deans’ self-assessment on the supervisory practices

Supervisory Practices	Teachers’ Assessment Scale	Description	Deans’ Assessment Scale	Description
1. Classroom Supervision	4.4	Always	4.09	Often
2. In-service Education	4.5	Always	4.5	Often
3. Teachers’ Evaluation	4.5	Always	4.0	Often
4. Community Service	4.38	Always	3.48	Often
5. Physical Plant Supervision	4.33	Always	3.83	Often

To test whether there is a significant difference in the assessments of the teachers and their deans regarding the latter's supervisory practices, a t-test was used. The findings in Tables 9-14 reveal that no significant differences exist, which means that the null hypotheses are accepted. This indicates that the teachers' expectations align with those of the deans, signifying cohesion and commitment between both groups of respondents.

However, when tested individually or by category, it was found that the supervisory practices related to teacher evaluation, as shown in Table 11, exhibit a significant difference. This suggests that teacher evaluation is the most crucial factor among the various aspects of supervision. Teachers demand an objective and fair evaluation of their performance that both parties should agree upon.

Comparison between the Teachers' Assessment of the Deans on their Supervisory Practices by College

Table 9 shows the differences in the assessments of the two groups of respondents when grouped by college. T-tests reveal that a significant difference exists in the College of Development/Arts and Sciences, Forestry Teachers College, and PTIA. In contrast, there is also a significant difference in their assessments in graduate school. This is expected because the setup in graduate school differs from that in undergraduate colleges. Graduate students are already professionals and mature individuals, which necessitates less supervision. Additionally, it may be that faculty members in graduate school are part-time instructors, making classroom and physical plant supervision less critical.

Table 9. Test of difference between the teachers' assessment of the deans on their supervisory practices by college

Supervisory Practices	T-computed	Decision
College of Development and Arts and Science	0. 32268	Accept
College of Forestry	0. 05828	Accept
PTIA	-0.8981	Accept
Teachers' College	-0.8981	Accept
Graduate School	0. 6822	Accept

Perceptions of the College Deans and the Teachers on the Implementation of Management Policies

The teachers' perceptions and self-perceptions of the deans regarding the implementation of policies related to promotion are shown in Table 16. Both groups of respondents share the same perception that the promotion committee is organized, with a mean of 9.5 among the teachers and 4.7 among the deans, both corresponding to the adjectival value of "strongly agree." Items regarding proper ranking for promotions and

the notion that promotions are based on existing criteria also received a “strongly agree” rating. Teacher respondents “agree” that performance rating is a consideration for promotion, scoring 3.8, while deans are uncertain, with a score of 3.3. On the other hand, both groups “agree” that promotions are well disseminated, with scores of 3.9 among teachers and 4.00 among deans.

The overall category mean value indicates that both groups “strongly agree” on the implementation of promotion policies. These findings align with favorable standards and are acceptable to the teachers.

Table 10. Teachers’ perception and self-perception of the deans on implementation policies relative to promotion.

Promotion	Teachers’ Perception		Deans’ Self-Perception	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Committee on promotion is organized	4.5	SA	4.7	SA
2. Promotion is based on existing criteria.	4.2	SA	4.4	SA
3. Objectivity is strictly Observed.	4.9	SA	4.0	A
4. Performance rating is a consideration for promotion	3.8	SA	3.3	U
5. Opportunities for Promotions are well-disseminated	3.9	A	4.0	A
Category Mean	4.3	SA	4.2	SA

The teachers’ perceptions and self-perceptions of the deans regarding the implementation of policies related to the reward system are presented in Table 11.

Generally, both groups of respondents “strongly agree” that recognition is given to deserving faculty and staff in the absence of promotion, that rewards are based on existing criteria, and that recognition takes different forms (e.g., citation or cash awards). Both groups yielded the same mean of 5.00, indicating that a coach/trainer whose team or contestant wins a national or international competition is recognized. They also “agree” that faculty/staff with inventions or innovations receive an award, with the same mean of 4.00. The teachers “strongly agree” (5.00) that faculty/staff with outstanding performances are recognized, while the deans are “uncertain” (3.00).

Overall, both groups of respondents “strongly agree” that the implementation of policies related to the reward system is favorable to both teachers and deans.

Table 11. Teachers' perception and self-perception of the deans on implementation policies relative to reward system.

Reward System	Teachers' Perception		Deans' Self-Perception	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Recognition is given to deserving faculty and staff in the absence of promotion.	4.8	SA	4.7	SA
2. A committee is organized to work on a reward system.	4.2	SA	4.0	A
3. Reward is given based on existing criteria.	4.6	SA	5.0	SA
4. Recognition is given in different forms (citation or cash awards).	4.6	SA	5.0	SA
5. Faculty/staff with an Outstanding performance is recognized.	5.0	SA	3.0	U
6. A faculty/staff with inventions/innovations is given an award.	4.0	A	4.0	A
7. A coach/trainer whose team/contestant wins in national or international competition is recognized.	5.0	A	5.0	A
Category Mean	4.51	SA	4.38	SA

The teachers' perceptions and self-perceptions of the deans regarding the implementation of policies related to professional development are shown in Table 12. Both groups of respondents "strongly agree" that there is a robust faculty/staff development program, that everyone is motivated to grow professionally, that the selection of participants is based on actual needs and duties for specialization, and that scholars serve the agency upon completion of the grant.

Both groups also "agree" that selection is based on existing criteria, and that everyone is encouraged to pursue relevant local and foreign-assisted training, workshops, seminars, and conferences. However, the two groups do not share the same assessment regarding adequate funding for scholarship grants to teachers; teachers "strongly agree," while the deans only "agree."

Overall, the mean indicates that both groups of respondents find that the policies related to professional development are being effectively implemented.

Table 12. Teachers' perception and self-perception of the deans on implementation policies relative to professional development.

Professional Development	Teachers' Perception		Deans' Self-Perception	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. There is a faculty and staff development program.	4.81	SA	5.0	SA
2. Everybody is motivated to grow professionally	4.6	SA	5.0	SA
3. There is adequate funding for scholarship grants.	4.2	A	4.0	A
4. Selection of scholars is based on existing criteria	4.6	SA	4.0	A
5. Everybody is encouraged to pursue relevant local and foreign-assisted trainings/seminars and workshops attended.	4.0	A	4.0	A
6. The selection of participants is based on actual needs and duties for specialization.	4.5	SA	4.0	A
7. Preference to training and development should be given to candidates with permanent appointments.	4.5	SA	4.0	A
8. Scholars serve the agency upon the completion of the grant.	4.45	SA	5.0	SA
Category Mean	4.45	SA	4.37	SA

Table 13 presents a summary of the perceptions regarding the implementation of management policies. The teachers have a higher assessment, with an overall mean of 4.42, while the deans have an assessment of 4.32. Both values are described as “strongly agree.”

This indicates that both teachers and deans have favorable perceptions of the implementation of management policies by the deans.

Table 13. Summary table on teachers' perception and self-perception of the deans' of CDCAS on implementation policies

Implementation of Management Policies	Teachers' Perception		Deans' Self-Perception	
	Item Mean	Description	Item Mean	Description
Promotion	4.30	SA	4.20	SA
Reward System	4.51	SA	4.33	SA
Professional Development	4.43	SA	4.37	SA
Overall Mean	4.42	SA	4.32	SA

Conclusions

This study concludes that the supervisory practices of college deans significantly impact policy implementation within their institutions. The findings indicate that while deans possess extensive supervisory experience and higher educational qualifications, discrepancies exist between their self-assessments and teachers' perceptions of their supervisory effectiveness. Teachers consistently rated the deans' practices as "always," particularly in areas such as classroom supervision and community service, suggesting a positive perception of the deans' roles in fostering instructional improvement and community engagement.

However, the deans recognized limitations in their practices, especially concerning resource allocation for instructional materials and opportunities for teacher professional development, attributed to budgetary constraints. This gap highlights the need for institutional support and funding to enhance the deans' capabilities in providing necessary resources and training for teachers.

Moreover, the significant difference in assessments related to teacher evaluation underscores the critical role of transparent and fair evaluation processes in promoting teacher effectiveness and aligning expectations between teachers and administrators. Overall, these findings suggest that fostering collaborative relationships and effective communication between deans and faculty members is essential for the successful implementation of educational policies and practices.

Recommendations

In view of the foregoing findings and conclusions, this study recommends the following:

1. It is highly recommended that college deans enhance supervisory support for faculty by implementing structured mentorship programs that facilitate regular feedback and guidance.
2. A focus on promoting collaboration among departments is encouraged for college deans to create opportunities for faculty from different disciplines to work together on projects and share best practices.

3. Investing in ongoing professional development initiatives is suggested for college deans to tailor opportunities that address the specific needs of faculty members.
4. Establishing clear communication channels between administration and faculty is essential for college deans to foster an open dialogue about academic goals and challenges.
5. Utilizing data-driven decision-making is encouraged for college deans to inform strategic planning and resource allocation, ensuring alignment with the needs of both students and faculty.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study, maintaining integrity, transparency, and respect for the participants' rights. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the study, with measures in place to protect their well-being. There were no conflicts of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The findings were interpreted without bias, and the results were used exclusively for the study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends her deepest gratitude to all those who played a crucial role in the successful completion of her research. She is particularly thankful to the participants for their assistance, support, and collaboration. She also acknowledges the invaluable guidance of her research adviser, the unwavering support of her colleagues at Cabatuan National High School, and the encouragement of her friends. Additionally, she is profoundly grateful for the love and care of her family. Lastly, she expresses her eternal gratitude to the Divine Creator for the gift of life and wisdom.

REFERENCES

- Abaita, R. S. (1994). *The division supervision as seen by classroom teacher in Northern Samar*. University of Visayas, Cebu City.
- Acera, F. S., Tan, M. R., & Alonsabe, O. C. (2023). Correlation of administrators' leadership practices and the teachers' performance among public elementary and secondary schools. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*.
- Akın, C., & Erdem, M. (2022). How Management Styles Predicts School Culture: A regression analysis study. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*.
- Aloyzius, A., & Kindiki, J. N. (2020). *Administration and management: A*

- determinant to organizational efficiency and progress. (A consideration to Henri Fayol's principles;
- Aniagboso, I. A. (2020). The role of administrators in efficient management of the university system in Nigeria.
- Anitsal, I., Anitsal, M. M., Latta, M., & Burns, D. J. (2020). PANEL: Changing expectations from department chairs in the dynamic environment of higher education.
- Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2017). Reframing organizations: Artistry, choice, and leadership (6th ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Bosetti, L., & Heffernan, T. A. (2021). The emotional and personal toll of higher education leadership. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 53, 103-105.
- Cahyati, E., Miranda, D., Windasari, W., & Cindy, A. H. (2024). Manajemen efektif pendidik dan tenaga kependidikan untuk menciptakan pembelajaran yang berkualitas. TSAQOFAH.
- Chan, A. H., Malek, M. D., & Bahari, F. (2018). Higher authority organizational stressors among higher education deans: A multiple case study. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*.
- Cotton, K. (2003). Principals and student achievement: What the research says. Northwest Regional Educational Laboratory.
- Davis, S. (2015). The role of deans in academic governance: A critical analysis. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 30 (2), 45-57.
- Farizi, A., & Patimah, S. (2023). Effectiveness of human resource management in improving the quality of government higher education in Bandar Lampung City. *International Journal of Educational Research & Social Sciences*.
- Francis, O. B., & Oluwatoyin, F. C. (2019). Principals' personnel characteristic skills: A predictor of teachers' classroom management in Ekiti State secondary school.
- Fullan, M. (2001). The new meaning of educational change. Teachers College Press.
- Gaviria-Rivera, J.I., & López-Zapata, E. (2019). Transformational Leadership, Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction in Work Teams. *EUROPEAN RESEARCH STUDIES JOURNAL*.
- Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Gordon, D. M. (2018). Supervisory leadership: A responsive approach.
- Goldring, E., & Sims, P. (2005). The role of the dean: A challenging position in higher education. *The Educational Forum*, 69 (3), 236-247.
- Harjunen, E. (2009). How do teachers view their own pedagogical authority? *Teachers and Teaching*, 15, 109-129.
- Kim, M., & Kim, S. L. (2023). Employee goal orientation and knowledge sharing: The moderating effect of leader boundary spanning behavior. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.
- Korkmaz, Y., & Koşar, D. (2023). Teachers' views on the influence tactics used by school administrators. *Gazi Üniversitesi Gazi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*.
- Lloyd, R., & Aho, W. (2020). The Four Functions of Management - An essential guide to Management Principles. Netra, Y., Zunaidah, Widiyanti, M., Yuliani, & Farla, W. (2024). THE EFFECT OF SUPERVISION AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE IN THE TIRTA RAJA DRINKING WATER REGIONAL COMPANY (PDAM), OGAN KOMERING ULU REGENCY. *Jurnal Syntax*

- Transformation*. Pace, J. L., & Hemmings, A. B. (2006). Understanding classroom authority as a social construction.
- Oyewole, B.K., & Alonge, H.O. (2013). Principals' Instructional Supervisory Role Performance and Teachers' Motivation in Ekiti Central Senatorial District of Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3, 295.
- Schwanenberger, M., Dereshiwsky, M. I., & Sujo-Montes, L. E. (2021). Administrative perceptions regarding supervision of online teaching and learning. *Education Sciences*.
- Sergiovanni, T. J. (2009). *The principalship: A reflective practice perspective* (6th ed.). Allyn & Bacon.
- Shen, J. (2019). Leading schools to success: The role of deans. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 57 (2), 177-189.
- Urdas, M. L. T. (1997). Management practice of secondary school heads in the district of Sta. Ana, Cagayan.
- Wang, L., & Holcombe, R. (2010). The importance of faculty evaluations: A study of faculty perceptions. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 48 (4), 494-505.
- Wepner, S. B., Henk, W. A., Clark Johnson, V., & Lovell, S. (2014). The importance of academic deans' interpersonal/negotiating skills as leaders. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 18, 124-130.
- Woods, P., & Wright, D. (2015). Creating a learning environment: The role of educational leadership. *Educational Review*, 67(2), 220-238
-